

Response to reviewer comments on TEBT-2023-0001

Manuscript title

Using bench protocol platforms to improve compliance with systematic review guidance documents and reporting checklists: proof of concept

(Previously: “A general-purpose protocol for facilitating standards compliance when planning systematic reviews”)

General comments for editor and reviewers

We are very grateful for the thoughtful and constructive comments provided by the reviewers and editor. Thank you!

We wholeheartedly agree that we could have been much clearer about the objectives and target audience of this paper. This would in turn have made it easier to understand what we were trying to achieve in our study. The editor’s and reviewers’ comments and guidance have been very helpful as we seek to address these issues.

To clarify, the primary goal of our paper is not to present a finished tool that novice systematic review authors would be expected to use. Rather, it is a more technical paper about why such a tool might be expected to be effective, and how such a tool could be developed. The audience is tool-builders and people working in research policy, not tool-users.

We have reframed the manuscript to make this clearer, removed confusing language around testing of hypotheses, been explicit about the target audiences, and added structure and changed subheadings to make it easier to follow our process and discussion. We hope this addresses the issues raised by the editor and reviewers. Detailed comment-by-comments responses are in the table below.

With thanks,

Paul Whaley, on behalf of the author team

Ref.	Comment	Response
Editorial triage		
1	<p>Given the objective of the work is to explore whether developing the operational process for SR protocol development would improve compliance with conduct standards and checklists (i.e. build theoretical understanding), there are issues regarding the structure of the manuscript and to what extent the current methods and results sections are aligned with this objective. A key question to answer here is whether the use of a hypothetical example for a SR protocol to demonstrate the use of the tool would be considered sufficient or if a real case study is necessary prior to publication.</p>	<p>We have attempted to make our objective clearer: it was less to explore how a standardised SR protocol could improve guidance- and checklist-compliance, but to explore what sort of technology stack would be needed to do this, and why it might be expected to work.</p> <p>A real case study is not yet appropriate. In our proof-of-concept we show that while there are good theoretical reasons for thinking compliance can be improved, currently available technology is too limited for building such a system at this time.</p> <p>Once more features around those we mention in our discussion have been introduced, the system might be sufficiently advanced that informative user testing could realistically be conducted. Right now, such user testing would be premature.</p>
2	<p>The structure of the manuscript is challenging. Whilst this is related to the topic and development of a tool, some material presented in discussion should be covered results (and potentially methods).</p>	<p>We have restructured the manuscript, especially the methods and results sections.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Methods” is now “system design”, to make clearer that we are building a tool rather than designing a study. • “Expected results” is now “Anticipated results of running protocol”, to make it clearer that it is about what using our tool would be expected to achieve. <p>This is a combination of attempting to meet PLoS expectations in how they expect protocols to be written up (see cover letter), and now also informed by Protocol Exchange reporting expectations as seen in e.g. Ruge et al. (2023)</p>
3	<p>This is an interesting manuscript; the development of the tool is important to the field and the work is undoubtedly worthy of publication. Potentially because it relates to the development of a tool, the logical structure of the manuscript is challenging. I would be interested in hearing reviewers’ views and suggestions in terms of organisation of the materials and presentation of results, i.e. what belongs to methods, results and/or discussion, with specific reference to the stated objective and</p>	<p>Thank you. We hope we have addressed the issues with the logical structure of the manuscript.</p>

	research hypothesis. Another important question for reviewers to answer would be whether running the tool for a hypothetical example is sufficient to demonstrate its the successful implementation.	
Assessment report		
4	<p>This manuscript is a proof-of-concept study aiming to set the initial groundwork to test the hypothesis that compliance with systematic review (SR) conduct standards and reporting checklists can be improved by reducing the amount of experience required for successfully using such standards and checklists. The authors developed code and a template for automated creation of a draft protocol manuscript. This allowed them to develop a theoretical understanding of how such a system may improve compliance with research conduct and reporting standards. They identified specific and general issues that would need to be addressed to enable further development and testing of the proposed approach.</p>	<p>From this summary of our manuscript, we can see clearly how we have miscommunicated our goals. In particular, using phrasing such as “hypothesis testing” or similar was a mistake, so we have eliminated it completely.</p> <p>All we really intended was to develop a proof-of-concept application, explaining why we think it could work, and explore the sort of technology stack that might be required to make it work. Testing whether such a system actually works would have to come later (not least, because we found that while the technology stack in current form provides proof of concept, it is not yet mature enough to create a system that could be meaningfully tested for effectiveness).</p> <p>We have made extensive revisions throughout the introduction and system design sections to make this clearer.</p>
5	<p>There is general consensus that the work is needed and of interest to the systematic review community.</p> <p>Reviewer 1: The topic is both necessary and pertinent.</p> <p>Reviewer 2: This is definitely of interest to the systematic review community but needs to be simplified somehow and considerations given to matters stated therein.</p> <p>Reviewer 3: This is needed work.</p>	<p>Thank you for the comments. We agree (especially on re-reading now) that the manuscript would benefit from simplification and revision, to clarify our aims and how we set about achieving them. We hope this is now clearer.</p>
6	<p>There may be some confusion regarding the aims and scope of the work described in this manuscript. Although the longer term aim is to test the hypothesis that the automated creation of a draft systematic review protocol may improve compliance with conduct and reporting standards, the aims of this proof of concept do not extend to actually testing that hypothesis. The aims of the proof-of-concept could be made clearer. Reviewers felt that the approach could also be clarified by</p>	<p>We have clarified that we are presenting a technical paper about why a general-purpose protocol might be expected to be effective, and how such a tool could be developed.</p> <p>The target audience for this paper is tool-builders looking to provide tools that support authors of SRs and people in research policy who may wish to understand what effective SR planning and documentation tools might look like and how they might work. At this stage we are not targeting the potential users of these kinds of tools.</p>

	<p>characterising the experience and understanding that may be required of novice users of such a tool as well as the background information and guidance that would need to be provided alongside the automated tool.</p>	
7	<p>Reviewer 2: There isn't much detail on the experience required for authors to undertake a review. There are concerns by the community that having a protocol template could allow authors to use this without actually knowing what they are doing and understanding the methods included.</p>	<p>We agree that misuse of tools, guidance, and checklists is a problem in research in general, and SR in particular. We are not sure if this is a good argument against the development and dissemination of such tools, because while they may be used badly, they may also be used well. Nor is it clear that the provision of the tool is the underlying cause of the problem as much as it is access to training, community expectations, and incentive structures and standards enforcement (etc) that are the root issue.</p> <p>Our contention here is that guidance such as COSTER and checklists such as PRISMA are helpful but challenging to comply with, because they do not present a complete, step-by-step account of what a researcher needs to do in order to fulfil the implied quality criteria that sit behind guidance and checklists.</p> <p>We argue that compliance can be improved by making explicit that step-by-step process. Because we make explicit that e.g. team selection is a key part of planning a SR, and we make explicit each core competency of the team, and planning process explicitly requires each competency to be accounted for by a named team member, it is difficult to see how the user of our protocol would not know what they are doing.</p>
8	<p>Reviewer 3: Our concerns are that tool like this should make clear for whom they are intended, and that if intended for novices, then full examples should be provided along with definitions and explanations for all relevant concepts.</p>	<p>This is a good point, thank you. Please see our comments below for our response.</p>
9	<p>The manuscript's primary issue is that it isn't clear who its audience is. It often reads as if it were about to introduce conducting a systematic review to a novice but then the needed background information is not provided and key terms are either not defined or not described in enough depth, making the tool better suited for experts who want to simplify a process they are already quite familiar with. Our sense is that the authors intend for this tool to be useful to novices. If so, much more background information will need to be provided,</p>	<p>We have clarified that our target audience is tool developers (see comments above). This is why we did not provide an end-to-end example of a systematic review or explain SR jargon, as we assume that tool developers will understand these terms and the general process.</p> <p>In this paper, we are trying to strike a balance between being intelligible to people who might see the benefits of the type of tooling that we are presenting, while providing enough technical information that a tool developer will find it informative.</p>

	<p>beginning with what a systematic review is, what one is used for, and how it differs from a routine literature review. Also, the examples that are provided are disconnected. We're not sure if we misunderstood them and they do form part of a single example but we think not. For learners to truly understand a new process, it's very important that a complete example, no matter how simple, be provided from beginning to end. Each step must be described carefully, with all new terms defined.</p>	<p>We do not think we can successfully introduce and define all technical terms relating to SR and tool development, at least not without making the manuscript unwieldy.</p> <p>Instead, we have (a) assumed knowledge of SR, (b) endeavoured to restrict the technical language of tool development to the "system design" section (as we are now calling it), and (c) written the rest of the paper as accessibly as we can manage.</p> <p>Hopefully this will allow the less technical reader to skip the technical parts and home in on the general discussion, maintaining accessibility while serving two audiences with different levels of technical proficiency.</p>
10	<p>Our recommendation is that the paper be reformulated as a guide to conducting SRs from beginning to end using the tool described here to ensure proper compliance, i.e. this is how you conduct an SR from start to finish and why (very important to clarify why things are done in given ways. Such a guide will then be extremely useful not only to novices, but also to e.g. instructors at libraries who are often tasked with teaching these kinds of skills. As such, a complete example with real information, even if it consists of a toy question, will also be invaluable. The key is that the different bits of documentation should have clear connections to each other so that learners can see and understand clearly how the different types of information in an SR map to each other. This is not clear in the example included in this version of the tool.</p>	<p>Hopefully our revisions and comments above have now addressed this.</p> <p>Once we are further down the road with development of this kind of tooling, maybe having something that can realistically be used, this advice to have an end-to-end example with detailed explanation of meaning of terms etc. etc. will come in very useful.</p>
11	<p>There is a need to clarify the intended audience for the current proof-of-concept, i.e. is the current proof-of-concept of interest for developers and experienced systematic reviewers, or presenting a tool ready to be used by novices? This represents editorial changes to improve the clarity of the aims and scope of the work presented, likely feasible and acceptable to the authors.</p>	<p>We very much agree! The current proof-of-concept is intended to be of interest for tool developers and people more on the research policy side, who might need to understand the shape of the solution but not necessarily all of its specifics.</p> <p>We have made extensive editorial changes to address this issue, and look forward to any feedback that might help us further clarify things for the reader.</p>
12	<p>If the tool introduced in this manuscript were already intended to be "an explicit, step-by-step sequence of operational procedures", further analysis and experimental work may be necessary to ensure the usability of the tool for novice users,</p>	<p>This kind of additional work will certainly be necessary for further development of this kind of tool. However, as we are only exploring immediate issues in a potential technology stack, we feel this work is outside the scope of the present manuscript.</p>

	e.g. develop background information defining key terms as well as guidance and fully worked example. This represents considerable additional work, may require additional funding and authors may select to instead clarify the aims of the current proof-of-concept template.	
13	There were no specific comment about the methods described to develop the general-purpose protocol. Reviewers identified the lack of user testing, either from SR specialists or novice users, as a major limitation of the work.	No comment.
14	While I recognize that this is a proof-of-concept project, I feel that feedback from users and systematic review writers who were not involved in the development of the protocol would be beneficial. Have the authors conducted any pilot testing and received feedback from users?	Please see comment 12, above.
15	Furthermore, to be effective and widely adopted by systematic review writers, the protocol should be user-friendly and easy to understand. It would be helpful to know if there is any training available or planned for the use of this protocol.	We absolutely agree! However, at this stage we are only presenting a theory as to why the protocol might be considered an effective intervention and exploring what the intervention might look like. It is not intended as a finished product so we do not, at this stage, anticipate training people in using the protocol.
16	There has been no user testing so it is difficult to know if this is a practical option.	The reviewers are being very generous in how they have phrased this: we ourselves are very confident that the application is not yet practical, due to a variety of serious limitations in the technology stack around data entry, export, and templating.
17	<p>The lack of user testing has been highlighted as a major limitation to the work by several reviewers. The authors identify that a number of modifications and improvements may be necessary before the tool can be user-tested. Depending on capacity and funding, the authors may choose to conduct user-testing before publication of this manuscript but this is likely to entail considerable further work.</p> <p>An alternative, as described in response to question 2 is to disambiguate the longer term goal and hypothesis that act as justification for this preliminary work from the specific aims of developing a proof-of-concept tool.</p>	As authors, we prefer the second option (disambiguating the longer-term goal) to the first, and have approached revising the manuscript accordingly.
18	There were no specific comments on methods or code. However, the readability of the manuscript	We have added a definition to the term “run” in the “automated documentation” section of the revised

	<p>and accessibility to a wider audience may be improved if language associated with development of software or automated tools was briefly explained and clarified.</p>	<p>manuscript. Terms such as “JSON”, API”, “authentication standard”, “structured DB” etc. we feel should be familiar to our target audience.</p> <p>We are concerned that defining all technical terms will make the manuscript unwieldy. We also think most of the terms should be familiar to our target audience (see also comment 9, where to aid readability we have tried to restrict technical development vocabulary to the “system design” section).</p> <p>We appreciate this is technical work and we probably do not have the best perspective on which terms are intuitive to understand and which are not. If the reviewers could indicate any terms in particular that the reviewers think it would be helpful for us to define, we would be glad to do so.</p>
19	<p>The manuscript was difficult to read. In order to make it more useful, the language and layout should be considered again as to where it could be improved to make it easier to read.</p>	<p>We hope that our revisions to the layout and language of the manuscript have made it easier to read.</p>
20	<p>There were no changes to the methods for development of the tool suggested, only that the language used be clarified to increase the readability of the work and its acceptability to its intended audience. This represent non-negligible editorial changes but should be feasible and acceptable to the authors.</p>	<p>The editorial changes were necessary and feasible. We appreciate the clarity and constructiveness of the reviewers’ comments.</p>
21	<p>There were no additional comments related specifically to findings and conclusions.</p>	<p>No comment</p>
22	<p>The authors should provide the spelled-out version and the abbreviated form of any acronyms or abbreviations the first time they are used in the text. For instance, in the first paragraph of the Materials and Methods section (P4), "PW" is abbreviated and in line two of page six, "API" is abbreviated without being spelled out first.</p>	<p>In general we would prefer not to spell out acronyms when the acronym is conventionally used as the name of the object in question rather than the string of words it represents (e.g. MECIR, PRISMA, PRISMA-P, etc.). When reporting which author performed a task, it is convention to use the initials without spelling them out.</p> <p>One could argue either way, but we feel that spelling out these lengthy phrases also detracts from the readability of the manuscript (particularly when so many of these acronyms stand for tortured phrasing), so we are in a situation of choosing the least bad option.</p> <p>The acronyms are all referenced in full in the bibliography. However, if the reviewers have a strong preference for spelling out all acronyms, we will do so.</p>

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The reference manager mentioned in Figure 3 is "Zotero", not "Endnote 20" – P7/L6

Well spotted! We have corrected this.